

PROCESSES FROM HALLIDAY'S SYSTEMIC FUNCTIONAL GRAMMAR AND CHAFE'S VIEWPOINT-MEANING AND THE STRUCTURE OF LANGUAGE

Sy Thi Thom

Commando College of Training Officers

Email: thomtsqdc@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper is conducted to present processes from Chafe's viewpoint (1970) and those in terms of Halliday's systemic functional grammar (2004). The descriptive method is mainly employed to give presentation on the processes with assistance of typical illustration examples by these linguists, and in order to find out the similarities and differences of processes from two above perspectives. In addition, to highlight the effect of Chafe's and Halliday's viewpoints on language science, some examples from books or results from studies by other linguists that followed these two authors' theories are listed.

Key words: Processes, process type, meaning and structure, structuralism, systemic-functional grammar

1 INTRODUCTION

There were a number of new trends of linguistics with various schools in the 20th century such as mentalist developed by Chomsky who had the foundation of structuralism; structuralist developed by Chafe, Bloomfield; systemic-functional grammar developed by Halliday and so on. As a result, one language concept can be understood in some ways depending on different viewpoints. Likewise, process mentioned in Chafe (1970) is not completely the same as that in terms of Halliday's systemic functional grammar (2004). Hence, what and how are process presented by Chafe and Halliday?

2 PROCESSES FROM THE VIEWPOINTS OF CHAFE AND HALLIDAY (2004)

Processes are to indicate verbs as they are considered in clause rank by both Chafe and Halliday when these linguists agree that verb is core element in a sentence. In details, according to Chafe, every sentence which is of interest to us is built around a *predicative* element. He also adds that usually, though not always, this predicative *element* is accompanied by one or more *nominal* element (1970, p.96). In other words, verb is core component in a sentence; nominal element is only to modify verb, and optional. It can be illustrated with the example: *Harriet sang* (Chafe, 1970, p.96). In the sentence, there is a predicative element *sang* accompanied by the nominal element *Harriet*. Furthermore, he asserts the nature of the verb determines what the rest of the sentence will be like, namely, it determines what nouns will accompany it, what the relation of these nouns to it will be, and how these nouns will be semantically specified (p.97). Sharing the

same viewpoint, Thompson writing *Introducing Functional Grammar* based on the theory of systemic functional grammar by Halliday stated that the process is typically expressed or realized by the verbal group in a clause, and is the central component of the message from the experiential perspective like the example: He *didn't look at* her (1996, p.77). It can be inferred that Halliday regards verb as a central element of a clause.

Besides, both Chafe and Halliday do not analyze verbs under the light of pure structural grammar. They consider and classify verb in meaning relations with other elements of clause. Under the Chafe's point of view, language in general, verb in particular are also concerned in terms of semantic structure when he shares that *without a knowledge of semantic structure, we are ignorant of the processes of semantic formation* (1970, p.73). Similarly, in spite of not mentioning semantic structure, Halliday (2004) ever discusses that three metafunctional lines (textual, interpersonal, experiential) can be unified within the structure of a clause. One of them is experiential function in which a *clause construes a quantum of change as a figure or configuration of a process, participants involves in it and attendant circumstances* (p .169). According to Thompson following his systemic functional grammar also shares that the categories of verbs must be based on grammatical as well as semantic differences (1996, p.78). In short, processes are considered with combination of common sense and grammar.

However, Chafe's processes are presented rather briefly comparing with those presented in Halliday's functional grammar perspective. As mentioned above, Chafe concludes verb is central, the accompanying noun or nouns peripheral to it. Based on meaning of verb and its noun combination in sentence, verbs are classified into three main types, namely, states, processes and actions. The types of verbs are summarized in the table below:

Table 1: Types of verb in terms of Chafe (1970)

	States	Processes	Actions
Definition	Verb is specified as a state, as is typical true of such a verb, it is accompanied by a noun-its patient.	Verb has been further specified as a process. Since a process still involves a relation between a noun and a state. - The noun is said to have change its state or condition.	Verb has nothing to do with either a state or a change of state. It expresses an activity or action, something which some does.
Examples	(1) The wood is dry. The disk is broken. The elephant is dead.	(2) The wood dried. The disk broke. The elephant died.	(3) Michael ran. The men laughed. Harriet sang.
Noun accompanying	patient	patient	agent
Verb	ambient		ambient

It shows that process, one of three types of verbs, can be distinguished from the rest ones based on several aspects. While **states** indicate a certain noun (wood, dish, elephant) is said to be in a certain state or condition (dry, broken, dead) in set (1); **actions** mean that verbs express an activity or action like in set (3); then **processes** where the noun is said to have changed its state or condition with illustration examples in set (2). Besides, another way to distinguish process from the others is which question it is able to be answered. In details, an action sentence answers the question *What did N do?* Like *What did Harried do?* The answer is *she sang*. However, a process sentence can answer the question *What happened to N?* that an action one cannot answer as examples follows:

What happened to Harried?

She died.

But not

She sang. (Chafe, 1970, p.100)

Discussing these types of verbs, Chafe mentions another aspect relating to identifying processes. They are *patient* and *agent* nouns accompanying process and action respectively. In addition, term *ambient* is given, too. Verb is called *ambient* in situation either verb is specified as a state with noun *it* being a surface element only, not reflecting anything at all in the semantic structure like such an example: *it's hot*; or verb is specified as an action like *it's raining*. However, process is not related to term ambient. In consequence, there are two sub-types of verbs: state ambient and action ambient.

Moreover, in certain sentences, verb is simultaneously both a process and an action. It means that as a process it involved a change in the condition of a noun, its patient; and as an action it expresses what someone, its agent, does. Let's see the examples below:

Micheal dried the wood.

Harriet broke the dish.

The tiger killed the elephant.

Hence, from the meaning and structure perspective, processes are presented and analyzed within relation between verb and noun in clause dimension under the light of Chafe (1970).

Beside from Chafe's viewpoint, processes are significantly deeply mentioned in terms of Halliday (2004). As mentioned above, according to Halliday, clause is a multifunctional construct consisting of three metafunctional lines of meaning: textual line of Theme +Rheme; interpersonal line of Mood +Residue; and experiential line of organization (2004, p.168). In details, experientially, the clause construes a quantum of change as a figure, or configuration of a process, participants involved in it and any attendant circumstances.

To discuss process from a systemic functional point of view, the term **transitivity** needs mentioning here. In the light of traditional grammar, even of Chafe, this term is familiar as a way of distinguishing between verbs according to whether they have an object or not. Here, from this

aspect, it is being used in much broader sense, referring to a system for describing the whole clause, rather than just the verb and its object. However, it still shares with the traditional use a focus on the verbal group because it is the type of process determining how the participants are labelled. Halliday argues that the transitivity system construes the world of experience into a manageable set of process type.

Under Halliday’s viewpoint, processes are classified into three main types: material, mental, relational; and three subtypes: verbal, behavioural, existential. Let’s look at the figure that representing process type as a semiotic space with different regions representing different type, as follows:

Figure 1: The grammar of experience: types of process in English (Halliday, 2004, p. 172)

First type of process here is material process that involves physical actions: running, throwing, scratching, cooking, and so on. In this case, material clause represents either a happening called **intransitive**, or doing called **transitive** as following examples:

The lion	sprang
Actor	Process

Figure 2: Happening represented by an intransitive material clause (Halliday, 2004)

The lion	caught	The tourist
Actor	Process	Goal

Figure 3: Doing represented by a transitive material clause (Halliday, 2004)

Another attention needs to be paid is when there is a Goal of the process, as well as an Actor. Hence, the representation may come in either **operative** (active), or **receptive** (passive) like the

examples: *the lion caught the tourist; the tourist was caught by lion* respectively. They are analyzed as follows:

The lion	caught	the tourist
Actor	Process: active	Goal

Figure 4: Operative transitive material clause, with process realized by active verbal group

(Halliday, 2004)

The lion	was	caught	The tourist
Actor	Process: passive		Goal

Figure 5: Receptive transitive material clause, with process realized by passive verbal group

(Halliday, 2004)

Besides material process, mental is a main type of process under the systemic functional grammar. According to Thompson, who paraphrases Halliday’s viewpoint of Functional grammar (1970, 1973, 1976, 1985a) in *Introducing functional grammar* (1996) writes that mental processes form a viable semantic category: there are clear difference between something going on the external world and something going on in the internal world of the mind. And the verbs refer to these mental processes, of thinking, imagining, liking, wanting, seeing, etc. Besides, here the terms *Senser* and *Phenomenon* are used instead of *Actor* and *Goal* in material clause (p.82). It is easier to understand when seeing the figurebelow:

She	Could hear	his voice
Senser	Process: Mental	phenomenon

Figure 6: Senser and phenomenon (Thompson, 1996, p.82)

In addition, here, to have an overall picture about mental processes within the relation among senser, phenomenon and types of sending as well, it can be seen the figure drawn by Halliday (2004, p.209) below:

Figure 7: Mental clause systems

The third type here is relational processes in which there is no process in the normal sense of “something happening” although there are always two concepts-one on each side of the relationship-there is only one participant in the real world. Take the clause as an example: *this bread is stale*. Here a relationship is set up between an object *bread* and a quality *stale*, and the function of the predicate is simply to signal the existence of the relationship. The relational process is quite complicated process type when relational processes have a number of types and modes of relation as the figure below:

Apart from these main process types (material, mental, relational processes) above, there are three less central types that can be distinguished on the basis of the usual combination of semantic and grammatical criteria. They are verbal, behavioural and existential processes. According to Thompson, verbal process are verbs of saying, intermediate between mental and material processes: saying something is a physical action reflecting mental operations. For example, *John said he was hungry* (Halliday, 2004, p.253). In this case, John is Sayer; said is Process: verbal. While behavioural processes are processes of physiological and psychological behaviour like breathing, coughing, smiling, dreaming and staring. For instance, *she waved her hands helplessly*, analyzed as follows:

She	waved	her hands	helplessly
Behaver	Process: behavioural	Range	Circumstance

Figure 8: Behavioural process (Thompson, 1996, p.100)

Last but not least, one of the three sub-types of processes is existential process that represents something exists or happens. For example, *there is a man at the door*. The analysis will be drawn for this clause as follows:

There	is	a man	at the door
	Process	Existent: entity	Circumstance

It is clear that in this case, the word *there* is neither a participant nor a circumstance. In details, it has no representational function in the transitivity structure of the clause; but it serves to indicate the feature of existence. In addition to verb *be* (usually used in existential processes), other verbs commonly occurring are mainly different from either the attributive or the identifying as the table below:

Table 2: Examples of verbs serving as Process in existential clauses (Halliday, 2004, p.258)

Type		Verbs
neutral	exist	exist, remain
	happen	arise; occur, come about, happen, take place
+ circumstantial feature	time	follow, ensue
	place	sit, stand, lie; hang, rise, stretch, emerge, grow
abstract		erupt, flourish, prevail

When discussing process types, it is necessary to pay attention to other participant roles and circumstances. As Thompson (1996) asserts that the role of Receiver in verbal processes is an oblique participant frequently appearing in a prepositional phrase. He also adds that central participants in a process are those which relate directly to the verb (Subject and Complement in terms of the Mood/ Residue analysis) (p.202). Besides the role of participant, circumstances giving background information also play a significantly important role in the process type analysis. They are often realized by nominal groups which are only indirectly linked into the clause by means of a preposition. Moreover, Halliday (1994, p.151) proposes nine main types of circumstantial elements, namely, location, extent, manner, cause, contingency, accompaniment, role, matter, and angle.

In short, together with the general category meaning of process types and the participant as well as their circumstances that are associated with each, Halliday (2004) gives a summary of types of process as the table below:

Table 3: Process types, their meaning and characteristic participants (p.260)

PROCESS TYPE	category meaning	participants, directly involved	participants, obliquely involved
material: action event	'doing' 'doing' 'happening'	Actor, Goal	Recipient, Client; Scope; Initiator; Attribute
behavioural	'behaving'	Behaver	Behaviour
mental: perception cognition desideration emotion	'sensing' 'seeing' 'thinking' 'wanting' 'feeling'	Senser, Phenomenon	
verbal	'saying'	Sayer, Target	Receiver; Verbiage
relational: attribution identification	'being' 'attributing' 'identifying'	Carrier, Attribute Identified, Identifier; Token, Value	Attributor, Beneficiary Assigner
existential	'existing'	Existent	

3 CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the process under the Chafe' viewpoint and in terms of Halliday's systemic functional grammar. Besides sharing the same viewpoint about processes when the two linguists consider processes by analyzing verb and regard verb as the central component within its relation with other elements in a clause, they have different approaches to processes. From Chafe' point of view, processes are considered from the perspective of relation between verb's structure and meaning. Although his presentation on process is not prolong and detailed enough to independently employ as the theoretical or analytical frameworks for language research relating to processes, it exposes and provides the innovative ideals that other linguists from the same as his school, as well as in other schools concern and continue studying.

In contrast, Halliday (2004) gives relatively deep and detailed presentation on processes. When Halliday's systemic functional grammar appears, a new approach for language research in linguistics is created, too. So far, it has become popular both worldwide and in Vietnam. Systemic functional grammar in general, process types, in particular are object, theoretical or analytical frameworks for a big number of studies conducted all over the world. I am extremely expressed by the classification of Levin's (1993) verb classes according to the system of Process type (cited in Matthiessen, 2013, p.139), therefore I would like to show his figure here as an example illustrating for Halliday's contribution to other research in the conclusion of this paper, as follows:

In Vietnam, Dr. Hoang Van Van, Dr. Phan Van Hoa are pioneers in the systemic functional grammar by Halliday. In particular, for processes, the number of research such as articles, theses, dissertations and so on conducted on them is so great. In conclusion, though Halliday' theory and Chafe's viewpoint about processes are not the same, *they are not exclusive, but of the same continuum* (Le Van Canh, 2011, p.). Their contributions to linguistics in general and verb analysis within a clause in particular are so great. Even their limitations also helps open another approaches that linguists need to find out and apply in linguistics.

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